

ANALYSIS OF SYMBOLIC IMAGES IN ALISHER NAVOI'S FRIEND "LISON UT-TAIR"

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Alisher Navoiyning "Lison ut-tayr" dostoni va dostonida qo'llanilgan ramziy o'brazlar tahlili haqida yozilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Lison ut-tayr, Mantiq ut-tayr, tahlil, talqin, ramziy obraz, semurg', Ilohiynoma, Ushturnoma, Lujjai hilol, Tazkirat ul-avliyo.*

Аннотация: *Данная статья посвящена эпосу Алишера Навои «Лисон ут-тайр» и анализу символических образов, использованных в эпосе.*

Ключевые слова: *Лисон ут-тайр, Мантик ут-тайр, анализ, интерпретация, символический образ, семург, Илогийнома, Уштурнома, Луджаи хилал, Тазкират ул-авлия.*

Annotation: *This article is about Alisher Navoi's epic "Lison ut-tayr" and the analysis of the symbolic images used in the epic.*

Keywords: *Lison ut-tayr, Mantiq ut-tayr, analysis, interpretation, symbolic image, semurg, Ilohiynoma, Ushturnoma, Lujjai hilal, Tazkirat ul-awliya.*

The epic "Lison ut-tayr" was written in the last years of the poet's life, in 1499. Candidate of Philological Sciences Sh. Eshonkhojayev created a scientific-critical text of the epic and prepared it for publication with comments. The volume of the epic in this edition consists of 193 chapters, 3666 bytes.

The epic "Lison ut-tayr" is based on a philosophical and mystical theme, in response to the epic "Mantiq ut-tayr" by the great Persian-Tajik writer Farididdin Attor. Alisher Navoi himself says in this epic that he read and memorized Mantiq ut-tayr with enthusiasm as a child:

I remember this conflict,
Who is in the middle of school?
Kim chekar atfol marhumi zabun,
One lesson from all sides un

In that case, the natural bulhavas,
"Mantiq ut-tayr" was a multamas.
You repeated the ball quietly,
I am so sorry to hear that.
When you hear the words,
He did not want to say anything else.

The epic Lyson ut-tayr traditionally includes an Introduction, a main part and an End. The introduction consists of 13 chapters.

The first chapter of the epic is dedicated to Allah. When Navoi writes that Allah created this universe according to a definite plan, he says that nothing in it was created by chance. He emphasizes that the miracle of God unites the four opposing elements (water, fire, earth and air) into a single whole in the human body, and that the purpose of creating the entire universe is human.

In the chapter, Alisher Navoi also says that Allah made man aware of His secret and exalted him with the crown of the Khilafah, and cursed Satan for refusing to worship him:

And with all his secrets,
Both the caliphate and Sarfarozi.
That is the stubbornness of her mother,
Ajzu soil is one of them.
Together, he was responsible,
Together, he is the one who gave it.

Chapter 2 of the epic contains a prayer. In the chapter, Alisher Navoi summarizes his past life and considers himself a sinner in the eyes of the Creator.

Chapter 3 contains the praise of the Holy Prophet - nat. In the chapter, Navoi thinks about the Light of Muhammadiyah, that this light existed before the creation of the universe, that it passed from Adam to the Prophet Shis, and thus through many generations, to the Prophet's father, Abdullah, and finally to the face of his son. Writes that he appeared as the light of prophecy.

The chapter also discusses the activities of the Holy Prophet during his prophetic years: he fought against the disbelievers, destroyed the idol of Lot, and conveyed to the people the truth that there is no god but Allah. At the end of the chapter, the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) and all his relatives, the Companions and the followers, are told that they are pure.

He is pure, his offspring are pure,
He is pure, and his companions are pure.
Anga greeted him every time with a thousand greetings.
I will rise with the people of the world.

Chapter 4 is devoted to the definition of the night of the Ascension. In it, the Spirit of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) came to the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) and conveyed the message of the Creator. It is thought that the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) asked Allah for the sins of his ummah and that Allaah accepted all the wishes of his beloved.

Chapter 5 of the epic is dedicated to the praise of Hazrat Abu Bakr Siddiq, the first of the four caliphs. Alisher Navoi called him a "faithful and sincere" and, through the art of tasbeeh, likened the Prophet to a treasure in a cave and Abu Bakr (ra) to a dragon guarding this treasure.

Abu Bakr al-Siddiq attributes the fact that he became the Imam of the Caliph after the Prophet as if the sun had set and the moon remained:

Instead, the imam became the mother of the apostle,
The moon is always in the sky.

Chapter 6 contains the story of Abu Bakr Siddiq. According to the story, when Abu Bakr Siddiq ascended the caliphate, a group of apostates demanded the abolition of zakat, one of the fards of Islam. The caliph said angrily, "The law of the Prophet does not change a single thread. Those who rise up against it will be answered with swords and bullets. "

Chapter 7 of the epic is dedicated to the praise of Hazrat Umar Farooq. Alisher Navoi says there is no one in the Islamic world who can tell the difference between right and wrong.

Chapter 8 is a story about Umar Farooq. According to the story, when they captured Hadrat 'Umar Madayin, a great treasure was accumulated. Hadrat 'Umar did not ignore this treasure and property: he ordered that all the treasure be distributed to the invaders.

Chapter 9 - Hazrat Uthman (r.a.) praises. Uthman was nicknamed "Zunnurayn" for marrying two daughters of the Prophet. Alisher Navoi says that the people called him 'Uthman ibn Affan because they collected the Qur'an:

The Mother of the Qur'an,
The mother of Osman bin Affan as the people.

Chapter 10 contains the story of Uthman. According to the story, one day the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) went to a deserted place to rest. Even when some noble companions, some saints

and nobles enter their presence, their situation will not change. Nevertheless, when 'Uthman entered the room, they gathered the legs that the Noble Messenger had stretched out. It was an expression of the Prophet's boundless respect for Uthman.

Chapter 11 is dedicated to the praise of the Commander of the Faithful, Hazrat Ali (ra). Navoi told the Prophet that he was a child and that there was a covenant between them: "I am yours, you are mine."

Chapter 12 contains a story about Hazrat Ali. According to the story, during one of the battles, Hazrat Ali was shot. The tip of the bullet sank to their bones, making it impossible to pull. When the Companions asked the Prophet, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, the Messenger of Allah, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, said, "Seek to shoot while he is praying. He will be given to the prayer in such a way that he will not know who took the bullet." The Companions did as they were told, and Allah, glory unto Him, did not inflict any pain or injuries on them.

Chapter 13 is dedicated to the great Persian writer Farididdin Attar. Alisher Navoi, figuratively speaking to the poet's pseudonym, says that the store is a collection of all the riches of the world: pearls, musk warehouses, sweets.

Alisher Navoi says that Attor's works are as useful as flowers for the people, and in this regard he lists his works: ready" and others. At the end of the chapter, Navoi says that if Haq helps me, I will get help from the spirit of Gado Sheikh and express the speech of birds, that is, I will write a reply to "Mantiq ut-tayr":

If Lek is right, I am gado,
The spirit of the sheikh.
Think of a bird's-eye view,
I speak like a nightingale.
Who can sing for the people?
Let us talk about bird language.
An example is the parrot point,
That is the decent thing to do, folks.
Who would want to date a parrot?
Unless you are a techie who knows,
What he is doing.
The grace of God is gracious,
I mean, it is from Attor's shop.

The main part of the epic begins with Chapter 14. One day all the birds came together for a meeting. However, there was a quarrel in the meeting.

They thought that if there were a just king, there would be no need to argue. At that time, a bird named Hudhud said that there was such a king, his name was Simurg, and that those who wanted to go to Simurg had to go a long and difficult way.

The birds set off under the direction of Hudhud. After a few days of traveling, the arduous journey exhausts them. They want to go back and apologize to Hudhud one by one. Parrot apologizes first. In response, Hudhud tells the story of a "man in a green cloak who has gained a trick." After the parrot, Peacock apologized, saying, "God made me to be seen and admired by those around me, so why do I need this trip?" Hudhud responds by telling the story of a clown Indian who decorated himself with various ornaments and performed in the square, and was surrounded by a gang of thugs, who were captured by the guards and beaten with whips. Then Bulbul apologizes. He says that he is in love with a flower in his bag, that he cannot bear to lose it and that this time he is infinitely tormented. Hudhud tells him the story of a gado who boasted that he was in love with a king. Thus, birds such as Qumri, Kabutar, Kabki Dari (Mountain Sparrow), Tazarv, Qarchigay, Shunkar, Burgut, Kuf (Owl), Humoy, Duck, Chicken (Rooster) they apologize. Hudhud responds to each of them with different stories in an appropriate situation. The birds continue on their way. They ask Hudhud about the way to Simurg. Hudhud tells them the story of Sheikh San'an, one of the greatest and most influential figures in the epic.

According to the story, a saint named Sheikh San'an was a murshid-teacher to all the sheikhs in the Kaaba. He had about 400 disciples, each of whom was equal to Junaid and Boyazid. If Sheikh Sanan saw something in a dream, it would happen right in front of him. One day he had a dream in which he was walking drunk in a temple in Greece. He wakes up and repents. However, after the dream was repeated several times, he realized that his interpretation was connected with his destiny and set out for Rome with his disciples. Finally, they arrive in Greece. There they see a strange temple. When the sheikh enters the temple, his condition changes and he becomes restless with anxiety. Suddenly, a tarso (Christian) girl appears in front of him with a veil over her face. When the wind blows and the veil on the beauty's face opens, the Sheikh loses his temper and falls to the ground. In this way, the Sheikh falls in love. Navoi describes his distress in the sheikh's language:

At the end of the story, the birds discover their Simurg.

According to mystical philosophy, this world is the manifestation of the Truth, the radiance of God. All beings in the world are the manifestation of

Allah. In this sense, man has to discover this particle in himself, and to do that he has to go a very long and difficult way. These are the seven valleys, as mentioned above. The last valley is the valley of poverty, that is, to become non-existent and join Allah.

Therefore, it can be said that Simurg is a symbol of reaching the Truth. Birds are a symbol of taxes claiming the rightful guardian. Hudhud is a perfect symbol.

As can be seen above, the epic *Lison ut-tayr* was written in response to Farid al-Din Attar's epic *Mantiq ut-tayr*. At first glance, the course of events in these two epics and the protagonists in them are the same. In fact, both authors differ from each other in terms of ideology and the artistic burden on the protagonists. Literary critic Z.Mamadaliyeva, in her study "The system of symbolic images in the epic Alisher Navoi" *Lison ut-tayr* ", while interpreting the symbolic symbols in these two epics, points out some features of Hudhud in the Navoi epic:

1) Hudhud in Navoi's interpretation is not only a symbol of a perfect man, but also the number one symbol of the author in the epic;

2) Hudhud, described by Navoi, explains the higher mystical issues with simple life events and examples according to the level of each bird;

3) Farididdin Attar begins the plot of his work in his epic by describing birds without any incident, and in *Lison ut-tayr* the task of describing birds is assigned to Hudhud;

4) Hudhud's mission ends when the description of the seven valleys in *Mantiq ut-tayr* comes to an end, but Hudhud in the Navoi epic also supports the birds in the last valley of poverty and death.

According to the author of the study, according to the idea in "*Mantiq ut-tayr*", the birds in it are just a shadow of Simurg. So, they would only resort to this as a last resort. The life of birds (humans) in this world is in hijra and separation. In Navoi, their creation is not in hijra and separation, but in the wisdom of the Creator. In this sense, we see that the two epics reflect two different interpretations of the philosophy of *wahdatu-l-wujud*. In Attar's epic, the birds unite with Simurg in the last valley, and in Navoi's epic, they purify themselves and discover Simurg while smoking.

Some of the birds in the saga can be interpreted as symbolic:

The beauty of the world fascinates the peacock.

The squirrel wants to rule.

The nightingale is in love with the fan world.

Kaklik is fascinated by one's behavior.

The eagle is an aimless power.

Chicken is deprived of intellectual and spiritual flight.

It turns out that many people can get into leeching with the claim of reaching the Truth, but not everyone can pass the exams and tests along the way.

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